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REPORT ON THE RESULTS OF THE SEMI-QUANTITATIVE CHEMICAL
ANALYSIS OF THE KENN REEF METAL SAMPLES
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Introduction

Three fragments of ship's hull sheathing plus 11 samples from ships' fasteners and fittings, all collected from Kenn Reef in Queensland, were analysed to determine their elemental composition (Table 1).

Table 1 Samples analysed for elemental composition, Kenn Reef, Queensland

Sample No.	Registration No.	Description
1	MA2200	Ship's hull sheathing
2	MA2201	Bolt with washer
3	MA2204	Ship's hull sheathing
4	MA2205	Spike
5	MA2213	Ship's hull sheathing
6	MA2217	Bolt (with wood attached)
7	MA2220	Pintle
8	MA2221	Spectacle plate
9	MA2222	Unknown large fitting, possibly rudder base?
10	MA2225	Strap with decoration
11	MA2234	Bolt
12	MA2248	Bolt
13	MA2252	Bolt (long, keel)
14	MA2260	Bolt w/ clinch

Sample preparation

Sample preparation for the sheathing (MA2200, MA2204, and MA2213) included embedding a small fragment of each sample in phenolic hot mounting resin for general use (brand: Struers MultiFast). The resin was added and set in a Struers CitoPress-10 hot mounting machine (Fig. 1). The mounted samples were then polished using a Struers TegraPol-11 diamond polisher to get clean, uncorroded surfaces for analyses (Figs 2–3).

From all other artefacts, samples were taken by drilling a few mg of material—for each sample a brand-new titanium drill bit (1.5 mm) was used to get an un-corroded metal sample to avoid any possible cross-contamination. Sample preparation included adding the drilled material from each fastener on 12mm aluminium stub with carbon tape tabs (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1. Struers CitoPress-10 hot mounting press. Photograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 2. Struers TegraPol-11 polisher. Photograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 3. Kenn Reef ships' hull sheathing samples embedded in black-coloured resin mounts after polishing. Photograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 4. Kenn Reef drill shavings mounted on aluminium stubs with carbon tape. Photograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Analytical method

Metal samples from the sheathing, fasteners and fittings from the Kenn Reef collection were analysed at Adelaide Microscopy, South Australia, using a FEI Quanta 450 FEG Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope (ESEM) (Fig. 5).¹ The FEI Quanta 450 is a High-Resolution Field Emission Scanning Electron and is used to image and analyse surface topography, collect backscattered electron images and characterise and determine a sample's elemental composition through x-ray detection with an SDD EDS detector.

¹ <https://www.adelaide.edu.au/microscopy/instrumentation/quanta450.html>

Fig. 5. FEI Quanta 450 FEG Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope, Adelaide Microscopy, University of Adelaide. Photograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

The FEI Quanta 450 with SDD EDS detector allows for a semi-quantitative analytical method of elemental composition by area or spot. As this method of analysis is a localized testing method, it is not necessarily representative for the composition of an entire sample. If possible, three areas per sample are tested to ensure they are characteristic. The areas chosen for elemental determination are those that display solid metal and are free of obvious surface corrosion (Figs 6–8).

The following SEM settings were used during data acquisition: High-Vacuum, Kilovoltage: kV 20, Element Normalized, SEC table: default, standardless. The time per sample analysis was automated.

For all the samples mounted on aluminium stubs, aluminium (Al) was purposely omitted from analyses as they may provide backscatter and interfere with the EDS detector probe. i.e. they can provide a positive reading for aluminium. The same can be said about carbon (C) as these samples are taped to carbon tape. Carbon inclusions are, however, clearly visible on the polished surfaces of the sheathing samples (Table 4, Fig. 8). Carbon is a known corrosion product that can occur as isolated inclusions in the actual metal a few millimetres below the surface (pers. comm. Animesh Bashak, Adelaide Microscopy). It is however known from 19th-century records that charcoal was sometimes added purposely to copper (Bennett 2021:293–294). For the purpose of this study carbon is simply omitted to focus primarily on the metal composition and ratio of metals in alloys.

Results ships' sheathing analyses

The ships' sheathing samples tested positive for the following elements: Cu (copper) and Zn (zinc). The complete elemental composition for the sheathing is listed Tables 2–5 and Appendix 1. Note that elements such as arsenic (As), silver (Au), bismuth (Bi), iron (Fe), lead (Pb), nickel (Ni), antimony (Sb), and tin (Sn) were added manually to the spectra and tested for as they are known trace elements in copper (cf. McLeod 1987). It also allows for an assessment of whether iron, lead, and tin are present in concentrations higher than trace elements would be, as they were often added purposely to copper alloys used for ship's hull sheathing. Iron, lead, and tin were however only detected in small amounts and are merely trace elements in the sheathing fragments.

Fig. 6. Cross-section of Kenn Reef sheathing fragment, MA2200, showing surface corrosion on left edge and metallic surface of the sample. Micrograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

The sheathing samples contain some lead as can be seen clearly in the micrographs, i.e. little white specks spread throughout the samples (Table 5, Figs 9–10). The presence of lead in the copper-zinc alloy is confirmed via spot analysis on the white specks, but their weight percentages are very low and vary between 0.15 and 0.41% (Table 5, Fig. 10). Such low weight percentages indicate that the lead is present as a trace element.

The sheathing was made of a yellow metal similar to Muntz and Williams Foster & Co patents with a copper zinc ratio of about 63–65% copper and 35–37% zinc (Table 3) (Chandrasekaran 2019; Van Duivenvoorde 2019b; 2020; Van Duivenvoorde et. al forthcoming).

Fig. 7. Cross-section of Kenn Reef sheathing fragment, MA2213, showing surface corrosion on the edges and metallic surface of the sample. Micrograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 8. Micrograph of sheathing sample showing spot analysis on one of the carbon inclusions, MA2200, Spectrum 2A.

Fig. 9. Testing area (frame labelled 'Spectrum 1') on sheathing fragment, MA2200, showing copper-alloy surface with small inclusions of lead (white in colour) and carbon (black in colour).

Fig. 10. Micrograph of sheathing sample showing spot analysis on one of the lead inclusions, MA2200, Spectrum 4.

Table 2. Elemental composition of the samples of ships' hull sheathing from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%										Total	Atomic%										Total
	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi		Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi	
MA2200: spectrum 1	0.07	0.08	62.76	36.29	0.19	0.00	0.06	0.02	0.38	0.16	100	0.08	0.08	63.67	35.79	0.16	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.12	0.05	100
MA2200: spectrum 2	0.08	0.00	62.03	37.18	0.18	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.41	0.01	100	0.09	0.00	62.90	36.65	0.15	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.00	100
MA2200: spectrum 3	0.07	0.04	62.79	36.12	0.26	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.32	0.16	100	0.08	0.05	63.73	35.64	0.23	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.10	0.05	100
MA2204: spectrum 1	0.04	0.01	64.09	35.14	0.24	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.10	100	0.05	0.01	64.95	34.61	0.20	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.03	100
MA2204: spectrum 2	0.01	0.00	64.61	34.89	0.12	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.13	100	0.02	0.00	65.41	34.34	0.10	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.04	100
MA2204: spectrum 3	0.05	0.00	64.23	35.09	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.35	0.02	100	0.05	0.00	65.07	34.56	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.11	0.01	100
MA2213: spectrum 1	0.14	0.03	64.02	35.23	0.27	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.16	0.04	100	0.16	0.03	64.79	34.66	0.23	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.01	100
MA2213: spectrum 2	0.08	0.00	63.53	35.70	0.21	0.00	0.15	0.01	0.28	0.04	100	0.09	0.00	64.38	35.16	0.18	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.09	0.01	100
MA2213: spectrum 3	0.15	0.02	64.63	34.50	0.35	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.01	100	0.17	0.03	65.42	33.95	0.30	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	100

Table 3. Copper-zinc ratio in the samples of ship's hull sheathing from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Ratio Cu/Zn		
	Cu	Zn	Total
MA2200: spectrum 1	63	37	100
MA2200: spectrum 2	63	37	100
MA2200: spectrum 3	64	36	100
MA2204: spectrum 1	65	35	100
MA2204: spectrum 2	65	35	100
MA2204: spectrum 3	65	35	100
MA2213: spectrum 1	64	36	100
MA2213: spectrum 2	64	36	100
MA2213: spectrum 3	65	35	100

Table 4. Elemental composition of carbon inclusions in samples of ship's hull sheathing from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%				Atomic%			
	C	Cu	Zn	Total	C	Cu	Zn	Total
Spot analysis: carbon inclusion								
MA2200: spectrum 2A	92.70	5.70	1.60	100	98.56	1.14	0.30	100
Spot analysis: carbon inclusion								
MA2248: spectrum 1A	39.66	60.34	-	100	77.66	22.34	-	100

Table 5. Elemental composition of lead inclusions in sample of ship's hull sheathing from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%				Atomic%			
	Cu	Zn	Pb	Total	Cu	Zn	Pb	Total
Spot analysis: lead inclusion								
MA2200: spectrum 4	7.44	5.11	87.45	100	18.97	12.66	68.38	100
Spot analysis: lead inclusion								
MA2222: spectrum 1A	2.15	0.57	97.28	100	6.60	1.70	91.70	100

Results of analyses fastenings and fittings

The analyses of the fasteners and fittings from Kenn Reef confirm the presence of three distinct groups of copper and alloys: group 1. pure copper (Table 6), group 2. yellow metal or copper-zinc alloy fasteners with some lead added (Tables 7 and 8), and group 3. yellow metal or a copper-zinc alloy fittings and straps with a high percentage lead additive (Table 9).

Group 1. Three samples of bolts from the Kenn Reef collection are made with pure copper (with the weight percentages varying from 95.17% to 99.46%) (Table 6: MA2217, MA2248, MA2260). These bolts likely came from the shipwreck of a vessel that was built prior to 1832. For comparison see the copper fasteners and fittings from other late 18th- and early 19th-century sites, such as *South Australian* (built in 1819, wrecked in 1837) in Victor Harbour, South Australia (Van Duivenvoorde 2019a; Zapor 2020). The copper itself is quite pure; it is not alloyed with zinc and contains little or no lead or iron.

Group 2. Three samples, two bolts and one spike, tested positive for the following elements: Cu (copper) and Zn (zinc) (Figs 11–12). The complete elemental composition of these samples is listed in Tables 7 and 8 (MA2201, MA2205, MA2252). These fasteners have a composition of about 29.25–33.57% zinc and 64.67–68.21% copper with small amount of lead, iron and tin which are low enough to be considered trace elements. These fasteners were made of a yellow metal similar to Muntz and Williams Foster & Co patents with a copper zinc ratio of about 66–70% copper and 34–30% zinc (Table 8).

Group 3. Five samples of a spectacle plate (MA2221), pintle (MA2220), an unknown large fitting, possibly rudder base (MA2222), a strap with decoration (MA2225) and a bolt (MA2234) tested positive for the following elements: Cu (copper), Sn (tin), Zn (zinc), Pb (lead) and Fe (iron). The group 3 samples have less zinc, but more tin and a significant amount of lead. The lead addition to this alloy is clearly visible in their micrographs (Figs 13–14). The complete elemental composition for these artefacts is listed in Table 9. These four fittings in this group were manufactured with elements varying from 55.61–70.02% copper, 10.72–28.51% zinc, 0.37–4.12% tin, and 5.32–29.07% lead. The copper-zinc ratios of the fittings show that they have a much higher copper content than the fastenings in group 2, for example (Table 10). The copper zinc ratio of MA2221, MA2222 and MA2225 varies from 81 to 86% copper and 14 to 19 % zinc. These three fittings are quite similar in composition. The pintle has a copper-zinc ration of 70/30 in all three tested areas. The bolt (MA2234) has a higher lead content that the ones in Group 2, but it is slightly lower than the fittings this group. Yet it is high enough to be considered an addition. If the copper-zinc ratio of the latter is considered (Table 10, 66–67% copper and 34–33% zinc), this fastener is more consistent with the ratios seen in Group 2.

Fig. 11. Micrograph of copper-alloy spike sample, similar in composition to the sheathing from the Kenn Reef collection, MA2205, Spectrum 1. Micrograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 12. Micrograph of copper-alloy bolt sample, similar in composition to the sheathing from the Kenn Reef collection, MA2234, Spectrum 1. Micrograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 13. Micrograph of copper-alloy spectacle plate sample, with added lead (white), from the Kenn Reef collection, MA2221, Spectrum 1. Micrograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Fig. 14. Micrograph of copper-alloy large fitting sample, with added lead (white), from the Kenn Reef collection, MA2222, Spectrum 1. Micrograph by W. van Duivenvoorde.

Table 6 Group 1: Elemental composition of copper fasteners and fittings from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%										Total	Atomic%										Total
	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi		Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi	
MA2217: spectrum 1	0.04	0.00	99.46	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.09	0.05	0.17	0.00	100	0.05	0.00	99.66	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.00	100
MA2217: spectrum 2	0.03	0.07	98.98	0.00	0.54	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.00	100	0.03	0.08	99.28	0.00	0.46	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	100
MA2217: spectrum 3	0.00	0.08	99.16	0.11	0.25	0.04	0.00	0.14	0.22	0.00	100	0.00	0.09	99.43	0.10	0.21	0.02	0.00	0.08	0.07	0.00	100
MA2248: spectrum 1	0.06	0.10	98.97	0.00	0.20	0.03	0.11	0.12	0.34	0.07	100	0.07	0.11	99.38	0.00	0.17	0.02	0.06	0.06	0.11	0.02	100
MA2248: spectrum 2	0.03	0.00	98.53	0.16	0.33	0.09	0.07	0.00	0.42	0.38	100	0.03	0.00	99.20	0.15	0.28	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.13	0.12	100
MA2248: spectrum 3	0.05	2.06	95.17	0.16	1.07	0.21	0.21	0.18	0.63	0.27	100	0.06	2.25	96.01	0.16	0.92	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.19	0.08	100
MA2260: spectrum 1	0.00	0.08	98.25	0.17	0.43	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.90	0.14	100	0.00	0.08	99.04	0.17	0.37	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.28	0.04	100
MA2260: spectrum 2	0.02	0.12	98.67	0.10	0.36	0.03	0.14	0.01	0.54	0.00	100	0.03	0.13	99.17	0.10	0.31	0.02	0.07	0.01	0.17	0.00	100
MA2260: spectrum 3	0.03	0.06	98.20	0.00	0.73	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.96	0.00	100	0.04	0.07	98.97	0.00	0.62	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.30	0.00	100

Table 7 Group 2: Elemental composition of copper-alloy fasteners with added lead from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%										Total	Atomic%										Total
	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi		Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi	
MA2201: spectrum 1	0.08	0.02	66.12	31.97	0.39	0.02	0.00	0.00	1.40	0.00	100	0.09	0.03	67.41	31.68	0.34	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.00	100
MA2201: spectrum 2	0.24	0.09	66.30	31.69	0.18	0.14	0.00	0.00	1.36	0.00	100	0.27	0.10	67.57	31.40	0.15	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.43	0.00	100
MA2201: spectrum 3	0.07	0.06	66.33	32.05	0.06	0.12	0.16	0.16	0.98	0.00	100	0.08	0.07	67.53	31.72	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.08	0.31	0.00	100
MA2205: spectrum 1	0.20	0.00	65.05	32.69	0.67	0.00	0.67	0.00	0.72	0.00	100	0.23	0.00	66.24	32.36	0.58	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.23	0.00	100
MA2205: spectrum 2	0.26	0.25	64.78	31.72	0.72	0.18	1.05	0.30	0.75	0.00	100	0.30	0.28	66.21	31.52	0.62	0.11	0.57	0.16	0.23	0.00	100
MA2205: spectrum 3	0.30	0.07	65.11	29.58	0.89	0.00	1.60	0.05	2.41	0.00	100	0.36	0.08	67.37	29.75	0.78	0.00	0.89	0.02	0.76	0.00	100
MA2252: spectrum 1	0.03	0.02	68.21	29.25	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.30	0.00	100	0.04	0.02	69.91	29.14	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.72	0.00	100
MA2252: spectrum 2	0.05	0.08	66.71	30.87	0.51	0.20	0.09	0.00	1.50	0.00	100	0.05	0.08	68.13	30.65	0.44	0.12	0.05	0.00	0.47	0.00	100
MA2252: spectrum 3	0.04	0.02	64.67	33.57	0.32	0.11	0.00	0.00	1.27	0.00	100	0.05	0.03	65.93	33.26	0.27	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.00	100

Table 8. Copper-zinc ratio in the samples of ship fasteners from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Ratio Cu/Zn		
	Cu	Zn	Total
MA2201: spectrum 1	67	33	100
MA2201: spectrum 2	68	32	100
MA2201: spectrum 3	67	33	100
MA2205: spectrum 1	67	33	100
MA2205: spectrum 2	67	33	100
MA2205: spectrum 3	69	31	100
MA2252: spectrum 1	70	30	100
MA2252: spectrum 2	68	32	100
MA2252: spectrum 3	66	34	100

Table 9 Group 3: Elemental composition of copper-alloy fittings and straps with added lead from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%										Total	Atomic%										Total
	Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi		Fe	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Ag	Sn	Sb	Pb	Bi	
MA2220: spectrum 1	0.12	0.02	65.14	28.51	0.24	0.00	0.65	0.00	5.32	0.00	100	0.14	0.03	68.43	29.11	0.22	0.00	0.36	0.00	1.71	0.00	100
MA2220: spectrum 2	0.12	0.09	63.23	26.96	0.08	0.27	0.37	0.00	8.88	0.00	100	0.15	0.10	68.13	28.23	0.07	0.17	0.21	0.00	2.93	0.00	100
MA2220: spectrum 3	0.17	0.01	63.12	27.57	0.31	0.02	0.47	0.25	8.07	0.00	100	0.21	0.01	67.68	28.74	0.29	0.01	0.27	0.14	2.65	0.00	100
MA2221: spectrum 1	1.52	0.09	55.61	10.72	0.13	0.04	1.54	0.00	29.97	0.38	100	2.21	0.12	71.19	13.34	0.14	0.03	1.06	0.00	11.77	0.15	100
MA2221: spectrum 2	1.09	0.05	66.33	14.21	0.25	0.10	1.61	0.07	16.30	0.00	100	1.41	0.06	75.73	15.76	0.24	0.06	0.99	0.04	5.71	0.00	100
MA2221: spectrum 3	1.20	0.05	69.09	13.47	0.03	0.13	1.21	0.00	14.36	0.46	100	1.53	0.06	77.73	14.72	0.03	0.09	0.73	0.00	4.95	0.16	100
MA2222: spectrum 1	0.79	0.13	68.01	11.93	0.39	0.02	3.17	0.09	15.48	0.00	100	1.03	0.16	77.75	13.26	0.38	0.01	1.94	0.05	5.43	0.00	100
MA2222: spectrum 2	0.71	0.10	68.03	10.83	0.17	0.00	4.12	0.12	15.93	0.00	100	0.92	0.13	78.41	12.13	0.16	0.00	2.54	0.07	5.63	0.00	100
MA2222: spectrum 3	0.76	0.00	67.34	10.89	0.15	0.13	3.43	0.00	16.80	0.48	100	1.01	0.00	78.17	12.29	0.15	0.09	2.13	0.00	5.98	0.17	100
MA2225: spectrum 1	0.51	0.00	64.04	14.71	0.43	0.04	2.56	0.00	17.71	0.00	100	0.67	0.00	74.37	16.61	0.42	0.03	1.59	0.00	6.31	0.00	100
MA2225: spectrum 2	0.68	0.09	70.02	15.79	0.28	0.23	3.29	0.23	9.38	0.00	100	0.85	0.11	76.62	16.80	0.26	0.15	1.93	0.13	3.15	0.00	100
MA2225: spectrum 3	0.59	0.03	69.32	15.49	0.13	0.00	2.96	0.12	11.36	0.00	100	0.75	0.04	76.74	16.67	0.12	0.00	1.75	0.07	3.86	0.00	100
MA2234: spectrum 1	0.13	0.03	62.09	30.99	0.25	0.00	1.20	0.23	5.08	0.00	100	0.16	0.03	65.41	31.73	0.22	0.00	0.67	0.13	1.64	0.00	100
MA2234: spectrum 2	0.13	0.04	64.46	31.51	0.25	0.10	1.39	0.12	1.99	0.00	100	0.16	0.05	66.47	31.59	0.22	0.06	0.77	0.07	0.63	0.00	100
MA2234: spectrum 3	0.13	0.09	59.66	30.25	0.61	0.12	1.19	0.00	7.95	0.00	100	0.16	0.11	64.17	31.62	0.56	0.08	0.68	0.00	2.62	0.00	100

Table 10. Copper-zinc ratio in the samples of fittings and bolt from the Kenn Reef collection.

Description	Wt%			Atomic%		
	Cu	Zn	Total	Cu	Zn	Total
MA2220: spectrum 1	70	30	100	70	30	100
MA2220: spectrum 2	70	30	100	71	29	100
MA2220: spectrum 3	70	30	100	70	30	100
MA2221: spectrum 1	84	16	100	84	16	100
MA2221: spectrum 2	82	18	100	83	17	100
MA2221: spectrum 3	84	16	100	84	16	100
MA2222: spectrum 1	85	15	100	85	15	100
MA2222: spectrum 2	86	14	100	87	13	100
MA2222: spectrum 3	86	14	100	86	14	100
MA2225: spectrum 1	81	19	100	82	18	100
MA2225: spectrum 2	82	18	100	82	18	100
MA2225: spectrum 3	82	18	100	82	18	100
MA2234: spectrum 1	67	33	100	67	33	100
MA2234: spectrum 2	67	33	100	68	32	100
MA2234: spectrum 3	66	34	100	67	33	100

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APPENDIX 1: SPECTRA KENN REEF COLLECTION

MA 2200

MA2200 Spot

MA 2201

MA 2204

MA 2205

MA 2213

MA 2217

MA 2220

MA 2221

MA 2222

MA2222 Spot

MA 2225

MA 2234

MA 2248

MA2248 Spot

MA 2252

MA 2260

